

Calculation of Electron Energy Spectrum of Quantum-Dimensional Structures

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Abstract:

It was studied a methodology to obtain the electron energy spectrum of a quantum well with infinitely high walls, an infinitely long cylindrical quantum wire, a superlattice of quantum wells and a stack of quantum dots. The specific examples of the spectra for nanostructures based on PbSe and PbS were provided. It was shown the possibility to use the results of calculation of the energy spectrum the simplest quantum-size structures for similar calculations in nanostructures of higher complexity and found the way to control the properties of a stack of quantum dots changing its geometric characteristics.

Keywords: energy spectrum, nanostructures, quantum-size effects.

Introduction

Calculation of thermoelectric (TE) parameters of nanoobjects - quantum wells (QW), wires (QW), dots (QD) and superlattices - usually consists of three stages. At the first stage, the problem is to find possible states of the main carrier in a nanostructure. Further, based on the received energy spectrum, the relaxation time is sought for a specific carrier scattering mechanism. In the case of thermoelectric phenomena, the interaction of electrons with acoustic phonons is considered, which is dominant at room temperatures. The calculation of the transport coefficients - the Zeebeck coefficient (S), electro- (σ) and thermal conductivity (γ) - is carried out at a third stage as a result of solution of Boltzmann equation solution. Such an approach is called semiclassical [1].

The model of a quantum well is convenient to use for the description of transport processes in thin films. The prospect of a significant increase of thermoelectric figure of merit ZT of the nanotube, in particular at the decrease of its diameter [2] and the possibility of synthesizing both arrays and individual nanowires [3] leads to the need to calculate the optimal values of kinetic coefficients in them.

If under a superlattice a periodic structure is understood as a sequence of independent quantum wells [4,5] - the multiple quantum well (MQW), - then, in this case, the energy spectrum is searched the same way as for one QW. The depth of real potential wells in superlattices is limited. The solution of the stationary Schrödinger equation for a one-dimensional potential well of finite depth can be found in handbooks on quantum mechanics [6]. In [5], it was shown that with the decrease in the depth of the well there are reduced both the number of bound states and the distance between them, but the state with $n = 1$ exists at any barrier height. Thus, in all potential wells in MQW, for each type of carrier, there is at least one bound state. The experimental confirmation of this property [4] allowed the application of an approximation of effective mass to describe the properties of particles in a potential well of finite depth.

Theoretical studies have shown that good TE properties can be demonstrated in a sequence of QD along a nanowire - a stack of quantum dots (SQD) [7]. The possibility of experimental synthesis of the stack and the structures on the basis of it [8] also determines the necessity of calculating the states of the carrier in it.

The purpose of this work is to present the method of obtaining and characteristic features of the energy spectrum of carriers in nanostructures of different types at the first stage of calculation of their thermoelectric properties.

I. Quantum wells

In a quantum well with infinitely high walls (Fig. 1), the electrons are confined in the direction OZ, and in the X- and Y-directions their movement is free.

Fig. 1. A view of the potential of QW with impenetrable walls.

Fig. 2. The partially quantized spectrum of current carriers in QW with impenetrable walls [9].

Fig. 3. Dependence of the density of states on a width of QW with impenetrable walls at a given energy ϵ ($\epsilon = \text{const}$). The dashed line shows the density of states of a bulk sample [9].

The electronic wave function and the eigenvalues of energy under the condition of the parabolicity of energy zones are determined by the expressions [10]:

$$\psi = \left(\frac{2}{\Omega}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(ik_x x + jk_y y) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi z}{d}\right) \tag{1}$$

$$E = \frac{\pi^2 \square^2}{2m_z^* d^2} n^2 + \frac{\square^2 k^2}{2m_p^*} \tag{2}$$

where $k^2 = k_x^2 + k_y^2$, m_z^* - effective mass of the electron along the direction of confinement; $m_p^* = \sqrt{m_x^* m_y^*}$, m_x^* , m_y^* are the effective masses of the electron along axes OX and OY, Ω is a total volume of the layer, d is the width of a wall, n is the quantum number that acquires values of natural numbers.

As shown in Fig. 2, the spectrum of carriers in a QW consists of overlapping zones. Its characteristic feature is the presence of a finite minimum energy ϵ_1 . In accordance with the principle of uncertainty:

$$\varepsilon_1 \equiv \varepsilon(n = 1, k_x = k_y = 0) = \frac{\hbar^2 \pi^2}{2m_z^* d^2} \quad (3)$$

It is known that the reason for the nonmonotonic motion of the thick (d) dependences of the kinetic parameters of quantum-dimensional structures is an oscillatory nature of a d-dependence of the density of states. Summing up on all values of quantum numbers n, k_x, k_y, we can obtain an expression for the density of states of QW with a parabolic dispersion law [9]:

$$g_{QW}(\varepsilon, d) = g_B(\varepsilon) \frac{\left[\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}} \right]}{\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}}} \quad (4)$$

where $\left[\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}} \right]$ - the whole part of $\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_1}}$, that is the number of subbands, the bottom of which lies below the given energy ε ; $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_1(d)$ is the energy of the lowest level (3), and

$$g_M(\varepsilon) = \frac{(2m)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{2\pi^2 \hbar^3} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

- the density of states in a bulk sample, m is the effective mass of current carriers.

It can be seen from (4) that for the values of d_n when $(\varepsilon/\varepsilon_1)^{1/2}$ is an integer, that is when the bottom of any subband coincides with the given energy ε , $g_{QW}(\varepsilon, d_n) = g_B(\varepsilon)$. For other widths with increasing value of d, the density of states $g_{QW}(d)$ decreases in proportion to 1/d until the number of subbands below the level ε (Fig. 3) is changed per unit.

The number of quantum levels lying below the given energy is determined by the first addition of (2):

$$E_n = \frac{\pi^2 \hbar^2}{2m_z^* d^2} n^2. \quad (6)$$

Substituting in (6) the value of the Fermi energy E_F, we can find the width d, at which below the Fermi level there lies a given number of levels n. The difference between values of this width for two nearest levels determines the period of oscillations Δd , that is equal to the width d_{min}, in which the bottom of the lowest subband coincides with the energy E_F. Thus, from (6) follows:

$$\Delta d = d_{\text{min}} = \frac{\lambda_F}{2} = \frac{h}{\sqrt{8m_z^* E_F}} \quad (7)$$

As can be seen from (7), the period of oscillations of the density of states and, correspondingly, of the kinetic parameters of QW is determined by the value of the Fermi level and the effective mass of carriers of the well. Determination of the period of oscillations Δd_{exp} from the experimental d-dependences of TE parameters allows us to estimate the value of the Fermi energy, which, together with the value of the effective mass, characterizes a particular compound in the form of a quantum well. In addition, the change in the period of the oscillations of the d-dependencies of the TE parameters makes it possible to trace the change of E_F at different intervals of the width of the well.

II. Nanowire

It is convenient to use a cylindrical coordinate system for an infinitely long cylindrical quantum wire (CQW) with a radius R, made of material "1" and immersed in a medium "2" (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Model of the cylindrical quantum wire "1", placed in the medium "2".

The Laplace operator in a cylindrical coordinate system (CCS):

$$\Delta = \nabla^2 = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2}. \tag{8}$$

Since the potential $V(\mathbf{r}) = V(\rho)V(z)$ has cylindrical symmetry, the solution of the Schrödinger equation is convenient to look for as:

$$\Psi(\vec{r}) = \Psi(\rho)\Psi(z) \exp(im\xi); \quad m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \tag{9}$$

Using the approximation of separateness of the potential [11]:

$$V(\rho, z) = V(\rho) + V(z), \tag{10}$$

the Schrödinger equation takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \left\{ \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left[\rho \frac{\partial R(\rho)}{\partial \rho} \right] \Psi(z) + \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(z)}{\partial z^2} R(\rho) - \frac{m^2}{\rho^2} R(\rho) \Psi(z) \right\} = \\ & = \Psi(z) R(\rho) (E - V(\rho) - V(z)) \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

By separating variables, we come to the two independent equations:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \frac{d^2 \Psi(z)}{dz^2} + V(z) \Psi(z) = E \Psi(z) \tag{12}$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i^*} \left\{ \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d}{d\rho} \left[\rho \frac{dR(\rho)}{d\rho} \right] - \frac{m^2}{\rho^2} R(\rho) + V(\rho) R(\rho) \right\} = E_m^{rad} R(\rho) \tag{13}$$

Taking the bottom of the conduction band E_{c1} of the medium of QW as 0 and assuming that relative to a vacuum it is below the E_{c2} of the material of the barrier, the limiting potential will have the form:

$$V(\rho) = \begin{cases} 0, & \rho < R \\ V_0, & \rho > R \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

The effective electron mass is:

$$m(\rho) = \begin{cases} m_1, & 0 \leq \rho \leq R \\ m_2, & R \leq \rho \leq \infty \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Then (12) is the equation for the free motion of the particle inside the wire along the OZ axis. And (13) is expanded into two equations:

$$\frac{d^2}{d\rho^2} R_1(\rho) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d}{d\rho} R_1(\rho) - \left(\frac{m^2}{\rho^2} - k^2\right) R_1(\rho) = 0, \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{d^2}{d\rho^2} R_2(\rho) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d}{d\rho} R_2(\rho) - \left(\frac{m^2}{\rho^2} + \gamma^2\right) R_2(\rho) = 0, \quad (17)$$

where

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi^2 m_1 E}{h}} \quad (18)$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi^2 m_2 (V_0 - E)}{h^2}} \quad (19)$$

General solutions of the equations (16), (17):

$$R_1(\rho) = C_1 \text{BesselJ}(m, k\rho) + C_2 \text{BesselY}(m, k\rho) \quad (20)$$

$$R_2(\rho) = C_3 \text{BesselI}(m, \gamma\rho) + C_4 \text{BesselK}(m, \gamma\rho) \quad (21)$$

Since

$$\lim_{\rho \rightarrow 0} \text{BesselY}(m, k\rho) = \infty \quad (22)$$

$$\lim_{\rho \rightarrow \infty} \text{BesselI}(m, \gamma\rho) = \infty \quad (23)$$

by definition of the wave function $C_2 = C_3 = 0$. Then:

$$R_1(\rho) = C_1 \text{BesselJ}(m, k\rho) \quad (24)$$

$$R_2(\rho) = C_4 \text{BesselK}(m, \gamma\rho) \quad (25)$$

The condition for the existence of a solution of a system of wave functions for boundary conditions and their derivatives at the border of the interfaces

$$\begin{cases} R_1(R) = R_2(R) \\ \left. \frac{\partial R_1}{\partial \rho} \right|_{\rho=R} = \left. \frac{\partial R_2}{\partial \rho} \right|_{\rho=R} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

is zero of its determinant:

$$k \frac{\text{BesselJ}(m+1, kR)}{\text{BesselJ}(m, kR)} - \gamma \frac{\text{BesselK}(m+1, \gamma R)}{\text{BesselK}(m, \gamma R)} = 0 \quad (27)$$

The analytical form of the solution of equation (27) for the possible values of particle energy in a QW can only be obtained within the framework of a certain approximation. However, the system of computer algebra allows finding the exact solutions of this equation for a fixed number m by numerical methods.

The eigenvalues of the energy of the CQW are classified by the angular m and the radial quantum number s , which numbers the solutions of equation (27) for a given m , and also by the wave vector k_z of the free electron motion in the Z-direction. The general solution of the Schrödinger equation for the CQW has the form:

$$E = \frac{\hbar^2 k_z^2}{2m_1^*} + E_{ms} \tag{28}$$

Using compounds IV-VI for combining of nanostructures it can be easily reached the required value of the limiting potential V_0 . For a PbSe nanowire placed in the medium PbS (Table 1), the value $V_0 = \chi_{PbSe} - \chi_{PbS} = 1.4$ eV. If the radius of the wire is $R = 5$ nm, the solution of (27) gives 6 energy levels E_{ms} (Table 2), four of which correspond to the quantum number $s = 1$ and two – $s = 2$. It should be noted that the radius of QW R has a decisive influence on the number of energy states of the carrier in it.

Table 1. Electron affinity χ , the width of band gap E_g and electronic effective mass m of PbSe and PbS compounds [12-15].

Compound	χ , eV	E_g , eV	$m \cdot m_e$
PbSe	4.7	0.29	0.04
PbS	3.3	0.41	0.08

Table 2. Energy levels E_{ms} (eV) of the quantized movement of electron of CQW PbSe/PbS with a radius $R = 5$ nm, deduced from the bottom of the conduction band PbSe.

$m \backslash s$	1	2
0	0.1754	0.8723
1	0.4382	1.2983
2	0.7672	-
3	0.1354	-

III. Superlattices

If wells and barriers of the quantum well superlattice (QWSL) are selected in such a way that the positions of the edges of the conduction band and the valence band relative to the vacuum are positioned in them as shown in Fig. 5, a [16], then the potential acting on the carriers of both types will have a rectangular shape (Fig. 5, b). Then the parameters of the superlattice subbands can be determined from the solution of the Schrödinger equation for a simple one-dimensional Kronig-Penny model.

Fig. 5. Placement of the edges of the conduction band and the valence band relative to the vacuum level (dashed line) in certain substances not contacted (a), and in the compositional superlattice of type I (b). On the axis of the abscis, the spatial coordinate is deposited, and the ordinate is the energy [16].

Periodic view of the potential

$$V(z) = \begin{cases} 0, & nd_z < z < nd_z + a_z \\ V_0, & nd_z - b_z < z < nd_z \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

and multiplicative representation of the wave function

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = \psi(x) \psi(y) \psi(z), \quad (30)$$

leads to two independent equations of the free motion of the particle in the X- and Y-directions and to the equations

$$\frac{d^2\psi_1(z)}{dz^2} + \alpha^2\psi_1(z) = 0. \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{d^2\psi_2(z)}{dz^2} - \beta^2\psi_2(z) = 0. \quad (32)$$

in the direction of OZ, where:

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi m_1 E}{h^2}}. \quad (33)$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi m_2 (E - V_0)}{h^2}}. \quad (34)$$

where m_1 and m_2 are the values of the effective masses in the environment of the well and the barrier respectively. In (29) $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2 \dots$; d_z - period of superlattice, a - width of a well. The equation (31) describes the movement of a particle within the well, and (32) within the barrier. According to Bloch's theorem, a generalized solution of the Schrödinger equation with periodic potential:

$$\Psi(z) = e^{ikz} u(z). \quad (35)$$

The solutions of the equations obtained after substitution (35) in (31), (32) have the form:

$$U_1(z) = Ae^{i(\alpha-k)z} + Be^{-i(\alpha+k)z}. \quad (36)$$

$$U_2(z) = Ce^{i(\beta-k)z} + De^{-i(\beta+k)z}. \quad (37)$$

Substitution (36), (37) in the boundary and periodicity conditions of wave functions

$$\begin{cases} U_1(a) = U_2(a); \\ \left(\frac{dU_1(z)}{dz}\right)_{z=a} = \left(\frac{dU_2(z)}{dz}\right)_{z=a} \\ U_1(a) = U_2(a+b); \\ \left(\frac{dU_1(z)}{dz}\right)_{z=a} = \left(\frac{dU_2(z)}{dz}\right)_{z=(a+b)} \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

gives a system of four equations for unknown coefficients A, B, C, D, which has a solution when its determinant is zero. From this condition follows the transcendental equation of the Kronig-Penny model [17]:

$$\cos(kd) = ch(\beta b) \cos(\alpha a) + \frac{\beta^2 - \alpha^2}{2\alpha\beta} sh(\beta b) \sin(\alpha a). \quad (39)$$

In the approximation of the strong bond ($V_0 \gg 0$), the solution of (39) has the form [17]:

$$E_n(k_z) = E_n^{(0)} + \Delta E, \quad (n=1,2, \dots), \quad (40)$$

$$E_n^{(0)} = \frac{\pi^2 n^2}{2m_1 a^2}, \quad (41)$$

$$\Delta E = (-1)^n \frac{8E_n^{(0)}}{a\sqrt{2m_1 V_0}} e^{-\left(\frac{1}{a}\right)\sqrt{2m_2 V_0} b} \cos(kd), \quad (42)$$

and the general solution of the Schrödinger equation for a superlattice:

$$E_n(k_x, k_y, k_z) = \frac{\hbar^2 k_x^2}{2m_x^*} + \frac{\hbar^2 k_y^2}{2m_y^*} + E_n(k_z) \quad (43)$$

Fig. 6. The energy zones $E_n(k_z)$ of the quantized electron motion in the QWSL PbSe/PbS, counted from the bottom of the conduction band of PbSe. The width of the well is $a = 2$ nm, and the width of the barrier is $b = 3$ nm.

If the condition of sufficiently high potential is not satisfied, then the solution of (39) can be searched by a purely graphical method. The system of computer algebra allows by the change of axes on the basis of the ratio $k_z(E)$, which is found precisely from equation (39), to construct the dependence $E(k_z)$. By the next digitization, and the subsequent approximation of the graphs obtained, one can obtain analytical expressions of energy dependence on the wave vector $E_n(k_z)$ for the required zones.

Fig. 6 shows the dependences of the energy levels E_n on the wave vector k_z as the solutions of the equation (39) for the quantized electron motion in the transverse direction to the superlattice PbSe/PbS. By changing the width of well a and barrier b one can significantly change the distance between the levels, as well as to reach the zero value of the band gap and, respectively, the semimetallic properties of the superlattice.

IV. Stacks of quantum dots

The stack of quantum dots (SQD) is a sequence of quantum dots (QD) along with a nanowire placed in a certain material (Fig. 6). In this case, the bottom of the conduction band of the material of QD lies below the bottom of the conduction band of the host material, as in Fig. 5,a.

Fig. 6. Model of a stack of QD: a_z - height of QD and width of QW in a superlattice, b_z - the distance between the dots and the width of the barrier, d_z - a period of a superlattice of QD, R - radius of QD.

Fig. 7. Minibands of a stack of QD PbSe/PbS deduced from the bottom of a conduction band PbSe. $R = 5$ nm, $a = 2$ nm, $b = 3$ nm.

The cylindrical symmetry of a potential $V(\mathbf{r}) = V(\rho, z)$ proposes the form of the wave function in the form (9). Separating the potential (10), we come to two independent equations (12), (13). The solution (13) is carried out in the same way as for an infinitely long nanowire and leads to the equation (27). The periodicity of the potential ensures that the solution of equation (12) is similar to the way it was done for superlattices. As a result, we come to a transcendental equation of Kronig-Penny model (39).

The general solution of the Schrödinger equation for SQD has the form:

$$E_{nms}(k_z) = E_n(k_z) + E_{ms}^{rad}. \quad (43)$$

The choice of geometrical parameters of the stack is similar to those used in the calculations of the energy spectra of the cylindrical quantum wire (Table 2) and QWSL (Fig. 6). It allows us to use the obtained data to construct the minibands of SQD PbSe/PbS (Fig. 6). As can be seen from Fig. 6 such a stack has semi-metallic properties, since minibands with a quantum number $n=2$ and $n=3$ overlap. Getting the bandgap and, accordingly, semiconductor stack properties is possible in two ways. First, we can change the radius of QD R , thus reducing the number of levels E_{ms}^{rad} . The second method is to change the superlattice parameters of the stack: the height of the QD a and the distance between dots b .

Conclusions

The paper describes the procedure for constructing an electron energy spectrum of a quantum well with infinitely high walls, an infinitely long cylindrical quantum wire, a superlattice of quantum wells, and a stack of quantum dots.

For QW with impermeable walls, an oscillatory change in the density of states changes with a change in the width of a well. That is, by the change in the width of the well the values of its kinetic parameters can be controlled. It is shown that the experimental determination of the period of oscillations of the kinetic parameters of QW allows us to estimate the value of its Fermi energy.

For cylindrical quantum wire PbSe/PbS, the energy levels of the quantized electron motion along the radius were given, and for the QWSL PbSe/PbS - the energy zones as the result of the limited motion of the carrier in the transverse direction to the superlattice.

Using the geometric parameters of CQW and QWSL for SQD, its energy zones were obtained, which provided it with semi-metallic properties. Also, the ways to change the size of the bandgap or to overlap of zones the stack by changing its geometric parameters are described.

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